

Was the Earthly Jesus a Demi-God?

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Filters from the Greek Myths and Contradictions

Statue of Hercules, Son of Zeus and Alcmena (Adobe, 2024)

...demi-gods in the reviewed studies. This distinction is evident in the actions of Jesus's disciples during his earthly ministry, where they performed miracles in his name (Luke 10:17) and continued to do so even after his ascension (Acts 3:1-11), a phenomenon absent in the demi-god narratives.

For instance, Heracles's loyal companions, the Argonauts, faced formidable challenges in myths, but they relied on human courage and resourcefulness rather than superhuman powers. In contrast, Jesus's followers were empowered to confront challenges supernaturally, a capability demonstrated in the early Church and persisting today. While mortal followers of demi-gods lacked the inherent superhuman strength of the demi-gods themselves, Jesus's followers achieved similar and even more feats using Jesus's name, showcasing the transformative power of faith and divine empowerment (Acts 16:16-18).

Arnold (1917) highlights the dramatic death of Heracles (the Greek's greatest demi-god), who succumbed to a poisoned robe given by his wife, Deianira, leading to excruciating pain. In his final moments, Heracles constructed a funeral pyre on Mount Oeta, where thunder boomed, lightning struck, and flames consumed him. However, the death of Jesus Christ on the cross surpasses even this spectacle. As Jesus cried out loudly and yielded his spirit, astonishing events unfolded: the temple veil tore from top to bottom, earthquakes shook the earth, rocks split apart, and graves opened, with many saints rising and appearing in the holy city after his resurrection (Matthew 27:50-53). Jesus's unique death not only involved extraordinary spectacles but also led to the resurrection of others, a phenomenon absent in the deaths of demi-gods.

Furthermore, the events surrounding Jesus's death confirmed his divine identity as the Son of God (Matthew 28:54), affirmed by witnesses like the centurion. Unlike demi-gods, whose superhuman powers stemmed from their dual nature as half-human and half-divine, Jesus's birth, miracles, and the spectacles during his death illustrate his mystery as fully human and fully divine. This distinction, as supported by Pederson et al. (2015), shows Jesus's unique authority to impart power, attracting millions of followers across generations, unlike the fading cult worships of demi-gods and heroes that have transformed with civilizations over time (Bremmer, 2005).

Modern discourse within Comparative Religion often draws parallels between the figure of Jesus Christ and demi-gods from Greek Mythology, noting similarities in supernatural births and superhuman attributes. For instance, while Greek myths often portray demi-gods like Heracles as products of unions between mortals and celestial beings, the Bible presents Jesus's birth as the result of the divine intervention of the Holy Spirit upon Mary, emphasizing his status as the Son of God (Luke 1:35).

The Greek's perspective is further explored by Edelstein & Edelstein (1998), who highlight the romantic entanglements of Greek gods with mortal women, a theme echoed in modern media like the Netflix film "The Legend of Hercules" (Harlin, 2014). These mythological unions resulted in the birth of demi-gods possessing both divine and human qualities. Perseus was born to Danae when Zeus showed up in a golden shower (Mellenthin & Shapiro, 2017). Dionysus was born from Zeus's romance with Semele and Heracles also from Alcmena (García-Gasco, 2011).

Even the sea deity Poseidon had a soft spot for earthly ladies and with Aethra, he fathered Theseus (Roberts, 2009). The narratives of Zeus's disguises or transformations during these sexual unions portray his cunning and desire for mortal companionship, adding depth to the exploration of divine-human interactions in mythology and religion.

However, this portrayal stands in stark contrast to the biblical depiction, where the words of the angel Gabriel to Mary reveal the Holy Spirit's pure intention of bringing forth a being destined to save humanity from sin (Matthew 1:21). Unlike the frequent instances of Greek gods engaging in unions with mortal women, which often carried real sexual

Statue of Jesus Christ (Shutter, 2024)

undertones, resulting in the birth of demi-gods who were used as tools in divine conflicts, vehicles of vengeance, or symbols of heroism and legacy, the conception of Jesus was a divine event without disguise or transformation of the Holy Spirit to mate with Mary. This absence of deception presents the uniqueness and sincerity of Jesus's divine purpose, distinct from the mythological narratives rooted in Greek culture.

While claims that contrasts with Soskice (2017) may be made that Christ was similarly half God and half human like the demi-gods possibly because of the nature of his birth and supernatural miracles almost comparable to the superhuman activities which the demi-gods could do, Jesus himself emphasized that believers could achieve even greater feats than his own (Jn. 14:12), a claim not attributed to any...